

Ministry of Health of the Republic of Moldova

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FACULTY OF MEDICINE 2

Department of Neurosurgery

Graduation thesis

CARPAL TUNNEL SYNDROME

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Study program 0912.1 Medicine***

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Chisinau, 2024

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BLS	Bureau of labor and statistics
CPT	Current perception threshold
CSA	Cross sectional area
CTS	Carpal tunnel syndrome
ECTR	Endoscopic carpal tunnel release
EMG	Electromyography
FCR	Flexor carpi radialis
FCU	Flexor carpi ulnaris
FDP	Flexor digitorum profundum
FDS	Flexor digitorum superficialis
FR	Flexor retinaculum
MN	Median Nerve
NCS	Nerve conduction studies
NCV	Nerve conduction velocity
PA	Palmar aponeurosis
PCBMN	Palmar cutaneous branch of median nerve
PL	Palmaris longus
RMD	Repetitive motion disorder
RSI	Repetitive strain injury
SSCT	Subsynovial connective tissue
TCL	Transverse carpal ligament
US	Ultrasonography
WMSD	Work related Musculoskeletal disorder

INTRODUCTION

Actuality of the problem

Carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) is a common medical condition resulting in pain, discomfort, tingling and numbness in the affected person's hand and arm. CTS is a result of the median nerve entrapment or increased pressure on the nerve. Obesity, repetitive wrist activity, pregnancy, genetic predisposition, and rheumatoid arthritis are some of the risk factors. The intensity of symptoms in CTS can vary from person to person and can be categorized into mild, moderate, and severe. Hand discomfort, numbness, and tingling along the median nerve's distribution are the hallmark signs of the illness. The thumb, index finger, middle finger, and radial side of the ring finger may all experience these feelings, this unpleasant sensation can build up leading to weakening of grip strength and affecting the functionality of hand and subsequently affecting the patient's quality of life [33].

The most common mononeuropathies seen in clinical practice are entrapment neuropathies and out of these neuropathies median nerve entrapment is one of the commonest conditions. The constricted spaces through which the nerve traverses can be modified due to a variety of lifestyle, inflammatory and physio pathological changes leading to compression and eventually damage to the nerve resulting in irreversible damage. The entrapment neuropathies only impact a tiny area of the nerve, but the tremendous impact CTS has on the body, mind and economy necessitates a heightened focus on refining and advancing treatments and other areas of this condition to be further studied and analyzed. Due to the exact causes of CTS being multifactorial and precise causes remains mostly unknown, CTS is classified as an idiopathic condition [84].

The statistical data from the United Kingdom General Research Database assessed that the incidence of CTS was 193 per 100,000 in women and 88 per 100,000 in men. Regular assessment of CTS reveals that women between the ages of 45 and 54 are more likely to experience it, whereas males between the ages of 75 and 84 are more at risk. At 99 cases per 100,000 people, carpal tunnel syndrome is the most prevalent peripheral compression neuropathy. The diagnosis is still being made more frequently due to sophisticated diagnostic testing and greater public awareness. Eighty-two percent of patients are older than forty, and women make up 65% to 75% of the cases. About half of individuals experience bilateral symptoms because of the disease. According to estimates, the yearly economic cost of up to 500,000 surgical discharges occurs in the United States, with a value reaching \$2 billion [106].

The median nerve along its anatomical path, it can experience localized compression or irritation at multiple sites. The cervical spine is where the second nerve lesion most frequently occurs. In the individuals without symptoms around the cervical region, a clinical examination of

the cervical spine is advised to determine any significant degenerative changes. Patients with degenerative abnormalities in the cervical spine may present with localized neck pain or stiffness or both and aberrant distribution of pain, altered sensation. The sensations can also vary with the position of neck [72].

Understanding the pathophysiological mechanisms contributing to CTS is crucial for effective diagnosis and treatment. Recent advancements in neuroimaging techniques, such as MRI and ultrasound, have provided valuable insights into the structural changes within the carpal tunnel and surrounding tissues with CTS. Additionally, molecular studies examining the role of inflammation and metabolic factors in the nerve compression have expanded our knowledge of CTS at the cellular level [3]. CTS has emerged as a pervasive and consequential health issue in contemporary society. This musculoskeletal disorder, marked by compression of the median nerve within the carpal tunnel, poses a significant burden on individuals and workplaces alike. In an era characterized by an increasing reliance on technology and repetitive occupational activities, the prevalence of CTS has risen, making it a crucial area of investigation for both the medical and occupational communities [57]. The economic implications of CTS resulting from work related disability and healthcare costs, underscore the urgent need for a nuanced understanding of its multifactorial origins and effective intervention strategies [96].

Aim of the study: The primary aim of this research is to investigate the multifaceted landscape of the Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) comprehensively.

Objectives:

1. Analyze the role of genetic factors in predisposing individuals to carpal tunnel syndrome.
2. Assess the impact of occupational factors, including repetitive tasks, forceful exertions, and prolonged wrist flexion on the development of CTS.
3. Studying the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying CTS, focusing on molecular changes within the carpal tunnel and surrounding tissue.
4. Evaluate the diagnosis of CTS using advanced imaging techniques, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and ultrasound, in detecting structural changes associated with CTS.
5. Examine existing treatment modalities including conservative interventions, physical therapy, and surgical options.

The practical importance of the work:

Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) stands as a prevalent and often debilitating condition affecting millions worldwide. As our societies increasingly rely on technology and repetitive tasks, the incidence of CTS continues to rise, underscoring the pressing need for comprehensive understanding and effective management strategies. This thesis endeavors to delve into the intricate mechanisms underlying CTS, shedding light on its etiology, diagnosis, and treatment modalities. The practical importance of this research cannot be overstated. At its core, CTS impacts not only individual quality of life but also carries significant socioeconomic ramifications. Individuals afflicted by CTS often experience pain, numbness, and weakness in the hand and wrist, impairing their ability to perform daily tasks and adversely affecting their productivity in occupational settings.

Moreover, the prevalence of CTS extends beyond the confines of traditional workplace environments. With the ubiquity of handheld devices and computers in contemporary society, individuals across diverse demographics are susceptible to developing CTS due to prolonged and repetitive hand movements. Therefore, the implications of this research extend far beyond occupational health, encompassing broader public health concerns.

METHODOLOGY FOR SELECTING BIBLIOGRAPHIC SOURCES

To attain the aim of the study, a literature analysis was conducted. The selection criteria were as follows:

Inclusion criteria:

1. Database: PubMed, Medline, google scholar, Web of science
2. Type of articles: literature synthesis, meta-analysis, cross-sectional studies, and case reports.
3. Keywords: “CTS”, “NEUROPATHY”, “MUSCULOSKELETAL”, “PARAESTHESIA”, “REPETITIVE TASKS”, “NERVE DYSFUNCTION”, “COMPRESSION”, “MEDIAN NERVE”, “INFLAMMATION”, “ATROPHY”.
4. Most of the studies were published in the last 10 years, but the bibliography of the respective studies was analyzed as well.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Study published in languages other than English
2. Translational studies

Number of publications analyzed from the last 10 years:

2014-2016	13
2016-2018	2
2018-2020	6
2020-2022	11
2022-2024	23
Total	65

1. OVERVIEW OF CARPAL TUNNEL SYNDROME

1.1 Definition and epidemiology of CTS

Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) is a prevalent neurologic disorder characterized by the compression of the median nerve as it traverses the carpal tunnel—a narrow passageway located in the wrist. The carpal tunnel is formed by the carpal bones and the transverse carpal ligament. The median nerve, responsible for providing sensory innervation to the thumb, index finger, middle finger, and part of the ring finger, as well as controlling certain motor functions in the hand, becomes compressed due to various factors [130]. The most common entrapment neuropathy, known as CTS, is estimated to affect 3.8% of the overall population. Based on clinical examination and electrophysiological testing, 1 in 5 participants who report symptoms including pain, numbness, or tingling in the hands are anticipated to have CTS, with idiopathic CTS being the most common diagnosis in patients exhibiting these symptoms. There have been reports of incidence rates as high as 276:100,000 annually, and prevalence rates as high as 9.2% for women and 6% for males. It occurs in all age groups but is more common in females than in males. It typically occurs bilaterally, peaking between 40 and 60 years of age [46]. Compared to the 5% frequency in the US, the prevalence of CTS is significantly higher in the UK (7–16%) [128]. Biomechanical overload, or repetitive motion and strain, is the cause of a rise in work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) recorded in all Western countries. In 1998, CTS cases accounted for more than 60% of upper limb musculoskeletal illnesses in Europe that were identified as work-related. Workers in certain industries, such fish processing, have been found to have a 73% frequency of CTS [131]. Rather than indicating a true rise in the occurrence of CTS, these statistics may simply represent the growing awareness of this issue, which translates into a greater volume of reports. There is undoubtedly a rise in the number of CTS patients; however, this increase may also be related to a general increase in life expectancy and a rise in the number of diabetes cases. The prevalence of diabetes in patients is 14% in those without diabetic neuropathy and 30% in those with it, but the prevalence of CTS in pregnant women is estimated to be 2% [30, 86].

1.2 Historical perspective of carpal tunnel syndrome

Entrapment neuropathy that is most recognized, understood, and treated most readily is carpal tunnel syndrome. However, most carpal tunnel syndrome patients were identified as having compression of either the brachial plexus or the thenar nerve motor branch of the median nerve

throughout the first half of the 20th century [79]. There have only been twelve reports of surgery transverse carpal ligament release for idiopathic carpal tunnel syndrome as late as 1950. The confusion generated by the various signs of compression of the median nerve in the carpal tunnel can be blamed for the delay in correct anatomical localization of this compressive neuropathy, as can some intriguing breakthroughs that changed the course of early research in this field [87].

The term "carpal tunnel syndrome" (CTS) was first used in print just one hundred years after the first description of median nerve compression in the carpal tunnel was made in 1854 [96]. Prior to that time, patients exhibiting symptom, which we now know were caused by CTS, were occasionally diagnosed with acroparesthesia and occasionally with compression of the brachial plexus or the motor branch of the median nerve. The first account of a carpal tunnel release procedure dates to 1933; nevertheless, idiopathic CTS was not described from a clinical and anatomopathological perspective until Brain and Phalen's work. Since 1960, peripheral compression-induced neuropathies have been diagnosed with CTS the most often [105]. After the landmark reports by Putnam and Schultz, further investigations into carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) took a distinct turn. In 1909, Hunt began publishing reports focusing on thenar muscle atrophy as a distinct disease process, largely neglecting sensory complaints. Hunt attributed weakness and thenar atrophy to compression of the motor branch of the median nerve, emphasizing occupational overuse as a causative factor. This motor-centric perspective dominated CTS studies for decades, leading to the misconception that compression at the wrist caused only motor deficits [88].

Hunt's theory gained popularity, especially in conjunction with cervical rib excision procedures advocated by influential physicians. Despite lacking efficacy, cervical rib excision became the standard surgical care for CTS in the early 20th century. The clinical failures eventually prompted a reevaluation of CTS pathophysiology. In 1913, Marie and Foix conducted a groundbreaking anatomical study, describing the "hourglass" configuration of the median nerve in CTS. They proposed early surgical intervention to halt the progression of symptoms, a suggestion not explored for over 30 years, hindering progress in CTS treatment [103]. Around seventy years after Paget's initial description, Lewis, and Miller (1992) reported a case of CTS following a distal radius fracture. Trauma to the wrist gained attention as a cause of median nerve compression [56]. In 1933, Learmonth officially published on surgical release for post-traumatic median nerve compression, a procedure likely performed earlier by Galloway in 1924. Despite Galloway's initial success, the recurrence of symptoms underscored the need for further advancements in CTS treatment [61]. In 1947, Brain, Wright, and Wilkinson conducted a pivotal clinical study, detailing six surgical cases that elucidated the signs, symptoms, diagnosis, and pathophysiology of spontaneous median nerve compression in the carpal tunnel. They observed initial sensory symptoms of "burning and tingling" in the distribution of the median nerve and

noted subsequent motor findings of "thenar muscle weakness" accompanied by rapid muscle wasting. Their conclusion pointed to the pathophysiologic process involving "vascular degeneration" due to aging, leading to ischemia, reactive edema, increased pressure in the carpal tunnel, and a perpetuating cycle [88]. Building on Brain's work, Phalen, starting in 1950, published a series of influential articles over three decades, further characterizing carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) as a clinical syndrome resulting from median nerve compression at the wrist [81]. Phalen emphasized the significance of incorporating both sensory and motor findings for an accurate CTS diagnosis. Surgical intervention in three cases yielded immediate symptom relief, leading Phalen to conclude that ligament division sufficiently decompresses the nerve. He also recommended conservative treatments such as splinting and corticosteroid injections before considering surgery [81]. Notably, Phalen introduced the Tinel's sign as a crucial diagnostic maneuver, described as a "tingling sensation radiating into the hand" upon light percussion over the median nerve at the wrist. Phalen's lasting contribution to CTS diagnostics is the eponymous "Phalen's sign," a clinical test involving wrist flexion for 60 seconds, exacerbating numbness and paresthesia, with prompt symptom improvement upon release. Phalen attributed spontaneously occurring median nerve compression to chronic tenosynovitis, positing that any condition increasing the volume of structures in the carpal tunnel would compress the median nerve beneath the volar carpal ligaments [89, 90].

As of 1960, carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) and its therapeutic approaches had been well-defined, encompassing all instances of median nerve compression in the carpal tunnel. This evolution positioned CTS as an entrapment neuropathy that was easily identifiable and treatable. Presently, it continues to hold the status of the most frequently diagnosed peripheral entrapment neuropathy, with a reported incidence of 99 cases per 100,000 population. An increased occurrence of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) has been observed in individuals engaged in occupations involving repetitive manual tasks, particularly those requiring prolonged flexion or extension of the wrist, strong grip, torque maneuvers, improper body mechanics, or exposure to vibration. Occupations at risk include butchers, grinders, cashiers, meat packers, and small parts assembly line workers [107]. The association between occupational overuse and CTS has been a subject of contention since the early 1900s. In a 1966 study involving 654 hands, Phalen argued that CTS was not an occupational disease [90]. In contrast, Hunt posited that it was not the nature of the occupation but the character of movements and their frequent repetition that played a primary role in the etiology of professional palsies, noting the highest association with occupations requiring overuse of the hands and arms [45]. Work-related CTS has been most prevalent among individuals engaged in forceful, repetitive manual labor [42]. The relationship between computer keyboard usage and CTS has also been debated. While repetitive hand motion has historically been linked

to CTS, establishing keyboard use as a direct cause has proven challenging. Phalen's 1966 study of 439 patients found that only eight performed extensive keyboard work. A 1992 electrodiagnostic study showed no difference in median nerve latency between individuals performing extensive typing and those not involved in such tasks [102]. A recent clinical study by Stevens, involving 257 office workers with significant keyboard use, found that only 10.5% met clinical criteria for CTS, a rate like the general population [80]. While there is agreement that factors like repetitive and forceful gripping can contribute to CTS, the debate centers on the extent to which keyboard use imparts traumatic force to the hands. Currently, evidence linking keyboard use to the causation of CTS remains inconclusive, and there is a lack of definitive quantitative criteria. Musculoskeletal and nerve dysfunctions arising from repetitive movements, particularly forceful actions, awkward postures, ergonomic discomfort, and other job-related factors, are collectively referred to as repetitive strain injury (RSI) [108] or repetitive motion disorder (RMD). These conditions typically impact the back, neck, upper, and lower extremities, developing gradually over weeks, months, or years. While back issues constitute the most prevalent RSIs, upper extremity RSIs have seen a significant rise. Another term, work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSDs), as used by the Bureau of Labor and Statistics (BLS), has gained preference over the previous RSI/RMD nomenclature [104, 108]. WRMSDs encompass a broader spectrum of occupational injuries, ranging from fractures and lacerations to RSIs. A 1998 report by Szabo on CTS as an RMD highlighted an increasing incidence of WRMSDs; in 1990, they constituted 48% of all reported workplace illnesses, rising from 18% since 1980 [78, 115]. However, the most recent Labor Bureau report (1998) noted that both the rate and absolute number of WRMSDs peaked in 1993 and have been decreasing since then [126]. Amadio reported a more than 30% reduction in the number of CTS cases resulting in lost workdays, with a corresponding decline in the rate of cases implicating repetitive motion to 7.4 per 10,000 workers [8].

1.3 Pathophysiology of carpal tunnel syndrome

Mechanical stress, increased pressure, and ischemia damage to the median nerve within the carpal tunnel all contribute to the pathogenesis of CTS. In terms of increased pressure, normal pressure has been measured to range between 2 and 10 mmHg. Changes in wrist position can cause substantial changes in fluid pressure in the carpal tunnel. As a result, extension creates more than a tenfold increase in pressure, whereas wrist flexion causes an eightfold rise in pressure. As a result, repetitive wrist motions are substantial risk factors for CTS [117]. Carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) serves as a paradigmatic example of a chronic compression neuropathy. Insights into the pathophysiology of compression neuropathies have primarily emerged from animal studies, with

a limited number of pressure-related investigations conducted on the carpal tunnel in humans [116]. Interpreting the data entails grappling with the nuanced relationship between acute and chronic nerve injury.

In instances of acute compression neuropathies, a sudden surge in pressure induces local ischemia, leading to the collapse of capillaries in the vasa nervorum. Consequently, the nerve is deprived of oxygen, resulting in a physiological response marked by conduction block. This condition is swiftly reversible, and upon pressure release, there is a rapid return to normal nerve conduction [64]. Animal studies elucidate mechanical damage at the compression's edges, featuring invagination of the myelin sheath and shortening of inter-node distances, leading to a deceleration of conduction velocity [77]. These studies involved the application of a tourniquet around a limb, investigating pathophysiological and histological changes in the nerve in relation to compression force and the duration of compressive forces. Brief intervals of high compression resulted in focal slowing or conduction block, and the longer the compression interval, the lengthier the latency period required for recovery after releasing the compressive force. The most severe myelin deformity occurred at the cuff's edge, where a steep compression pressure gradient was present [66]. Compression neuropathies are characterized by many variables relating to the kind of external force application. External compression can be delivered in a variety of ways, including: (a) a low force that is present for an extended length of time; (b) an acute focal application of a big external force (e.g., Saturday night palsy); or (c) repetitive application of brief strong forces [66]. Compression may also be related with some combination of stretching, shearing, and/or application of compressive force. The physiologic response of peripheral nerve fibers to injury includes conduction block and slowing of conduction, but it can also include ectopic impulse production involving efferent fiber effects (such as fasciculation, myokymia, and so on) as well as afferent fiber effects (such as paraesthesias, pain, and so on). The conventional classification of nerve injury (neurapraxia, axonotmesis, and neurotmesis) is insufficient to characterize the bulk of pathophysiological abnormalities observed in CTS.

Chronic models are more applicable to human entrapment neuropathies, which can progress slowly and insidiously [66], because there has been no human research on this topic, we must rely on animal studies. Unfortunately, no animal models exist that can precisely and totally reproduce CTS. Surgical observations in human entrapments show thinning nerve in the zone of entrapment with swelling of the nerve at the proximal margin of the zone of entrapment. This could be due to axoplasm buildup, nerve swelling (edema), or fibrosis because of chronic inflammatory alterations. One report of nerve histology from a CTS patient who died of a brain tumor [132] showed substantial demyelination and remyelination in the nerve entrapment site. Large, myelinated axons were found to be significantly lost. The nerve was enlarged near the injury,

which was associated with increased perineurial and endoneurial fibrosis. The fluid pressure in the carpal tunnel varies dramatically with wrist position; wrist flexion increases the pressure eight times, whereas wrist extension increases it ten times [36]. The flexor retinaculum forms the roof of the carpal tunnel, which is a U-shaped trough made up of the carpal bones. The extensor retinaculum on the dorsal side of the wrist and the volar carpal ligament on the volar side are also formed by an annular group of ligaments.

Figure 1. Dynamic interactions of wrist tissues during flexion and extension [118]. (a) Elastic bands separated by a sequence of elastic longitudinal elements can be used to describe the tissues around the wrist. (b) The bands expand out during extension (dorsiflexion), stretching the longitudinal elements on the wrist's palmar side, and compress them when they are pressed together on the dorsal side. (c) Additionally, when the wrist is extended, the volar aspect of the joint capsule is compressed by the proximal edge of the carpal bones, which lessens the amount of space that is accessible. (d) The volar face of the joint capsule is pressed against by the proximal edge of the carpal tunnel when the wrist is flexed.

An annular collection of bands divided by longitudinal elastic elements best describes these ligaments. When the wrist is extended, the rings move closer together and compress the elements on the dorsal side of the wrist while spreading apart and stretching the longitudinal elements on the volar side (figure 1). Soft tissue has a very low longitudinal rigidity, which makes it easy for these components to buckle and wrinkle. When the wrist is bent, this analogy also applies to the skin, which is why it seems to stretch on one side of the joint and wrinkle on the other. The volar

carpal ligament presses down on the contents of the carpal bones because of wrist extension. Remarkably, this pressure is prevented from damaging the carpal contents by the flexor retinaculum. Additionally, when the wrist is extended, the volar side of the joint capsule bulges and the proximal edge of the carpal bones glides in the opposite direction across the concave surface of the radial head. The carpal contents will therefore be compressed between the volar carpal ligament and the volar sides of the carpal bones because of wrist extension. Furthermore, when a finger extends, the carpal tunnel and the volar carpal ligament are dragged inward by the proximal, thicker section of the finger flexor tendons. This results in a decrease in the amount of space that is available while also increasing the volume of the carpal contents. There would be comparable pressure effects in radial, volar, and ulnar deviations. This results in a decrease in the amount of space that is available while also increasing the volume of the carpal contents. The distribution of CTS-related paresthesia and discomfort varies greatly. Traditionally, the median distribution is thought to contain most symptoms (figure 2) [36].

Figure 2. Common numbness/tingling distribution in carpal tunnel syndrome [81].

Pressure effects in volar, radial, and ulnar deviations would be comparable to those in extension, but they would not be as strong. The radius and the carpal bones determine the lateral dimensions of the compartment, and the range of motion for radial and ulnar deviations is smaller than that for flexion and extension. Pressure from the proximal border of the flexor retinaculum pressing the flexor tendons and bursa against the radius head may be the cause of increased fluid pressure during wrist flexion. In the initial phase of clinically diagnosing carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), individuals often wake up from sleep experiencing sensations of numbness or swelling in

the hand, without any apparent signs of swelling. This can be accompanied by intense pain radiating from the wrist to the shoulder, along with tingling sensations in the hand and fingers, a condition known as brachialgia paresthetica nocturna. Shaking the hand may alleviate the pain in most cases, although the hand may feel stiff later. The second stage of CTS progression involves the manifestation of symptoms during daytime activities, especially when individuals engage in repetitive hand or wrist movements or maintain specific positions for prolonged periods. Patients may also observe a decline in hand dexterity, leading to instances of clumsiness and objects slipping from their grip. The final stage of CTS development is marked by hypertrophy or atrophy of the thenar eminence. At this point, patients experience a loss of sensory symptoms [37, 41].

Although carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) is primarily considered an idiopathic condition, various risk factors contribute to its prevalence. Environmental risk factors encompass prolonged positions involving excessive wrist flexion or extension, repetitive use of flexor muscles, and exposure to vibrations [34]. On the medical front, these risk factors are categorized into extrinsic factors that increase tunnel volume on either side of the nerve, intrinsic factors increasing tunnel volume, extrinsic factors altering tunnel contour, and neuropathic factors. The rising incidence of CTS is linked to increased life expectancy in the workforce and a surge in risk factors such as diabetes and pregnancies. Extrinsic factors increasing tunnel volume involve conditions that disrupt fluid equilibrium within the body, including pregnancy, menopause, obesity, kidney failure, hypothyroidism, oral contraceptive use, and congestive heart failure. Intrinsic factors causing an increase in occupied volume within the tunnel may stem from masses or tumor-like formations, often resulting from distal radius fractures or posttraumatic arthritis. Neuropathic factors, affecting the median nerve without necessarily elevating interstitial pressure in the carpal tunnel, encompass conditions like diabetes, alcoholism, vitamin deficiency or toxicity, and exposure to toxins. Diabetic patients, with a lower threshold for nerve injury, exhibit a higher susceptibility to CTS. The incidence rate for CTS in diabetic patients is approximately 30%, compared to 14% in non-diabetic individuals, while the prevalence during pregnancy is estimated at 2% [13].

1.4 Clinical and surgical anatomy of the carpal tunnel

The breadth and shape of the CT are impacted by wrist joint movements. Throughout the usual range of wrist motion, the tunnel's width significantly reduces, and because the tunnel's bony walls are flexible, the carpal bones move in relation to one another with each wrist movement. The CT pressure is increased by both flexion and extension. A flexing wrist joint was shown to drastically reduce the cross section of the proximal opening of the CT scan. This is probably caused

by the distal end of the capitate bone moving and the Transverse Carpal Ligament (TCL) migrating radially. When the lunate bone is forced towards the interior of the tunnel, it compresses the channel in an extreme manner [99]. The thick (2-4 mm) central portion of the Flexor Retinaculum (FR) is called the TCL. It is a short, broad, and robust fibrous band with an average width of 25 mm and length of 31 mm that is made up of interwoven bundles of fibrous connective tissues. It reaches the distal section of the third metacarpal's base from the distal portion of the radius. The third metacarpal's carpometacarpal joint is 10 mm away from the mean distal limit of its distal portion, whereas the capitate-lunate junction is 11 mm away from the mean proximal limit of its central portion [24]. Concerning the laminar structure of the Transverse Carpal Ligament (TCL) (figure 3), four primary laminae have been identified: (1) strong distal transverse; (2) proximal transverse; (3) ulnar oblique; and (4) radial oblique. The prevailing pattern typically exhibits a dominance of the distal transverse and ulnar oblique laminae across all layers of the Flexor Retinaculum (FR). In approximately half of the dissected hand samples, the superficial layer is characterized by a prevalence of the distal transverse and ulnar oblique laminae, while the deep layer is marked by dominance of the proximal transverse and radial oblique laminae. Consequently, the strong distal transverse lamina is likely excised during the final step of Endoscopic Carpal Tunnel Release (ECTR) due to its superficial location, potentially contributing to the frequent occurrence of incomplete release. Additionally, the nearly universal presence of the superficial ulnar oblique lamina increases the likelihood of scarring, potentially leading to radial shifting of the ulnar neurovascular bundle and influencing the Palmar Cutaneous Branch of the Median Nerve (PCBMN). In conclusion, minor complications of ECTR may be influenced by variations in the laminar arrangement of the TCL [48]. In another study involving eight dissected TCLs, transverse fibers were the most prominent (over 60%), followed by oblique fibers in the pisiform-trapezium direction (18%), oblique fibers in the scaphoid-hamate direction (13%), and longitudinal fibers (8%) [94].

The TCL divides into superficial and deep laminae laterally, yet it is linked medially to the pisiform bone and the hamate's hook. The deep lamina is attached to the medial lip of the trapezium's groove, whereas the superficial lamina is attached to the scaphoid and trapezium's tubercle. The flexor carpi radialis tendon (FCR) is contained in a synovial sheath that lines the tunnel formed by the two laminae and this groove. The volar carpal ligament, which crosses the flexor tendons as they enter the wrist and runs from the radius to the ulna, is where the TCL is most closely attached. This boundary is in line with the distal flexion wrist crease, which also passes through the proximal ends of the pisiform and scaphoid bones [127]. The middle section of the palmar aponeurosis (PA) is connected to the distal border of the TCL. The typical distance between the superficial palmar arch and the radial boundary of the ring finger, measured along its

axis, varies from 5.5 to 19 mm [101]. This distal border is located between 2.7 and 6.5 mm from the nearest aspect of the motor branch of MN, on average [114]. It is possible to see a palmar fat pad, also known as the "fat drop sign," overlapping this boundary directly proximal to the distal end of the TCL and parallel to the ring finger's axis. It is a dependable anatomic landmark that needs to be retracted to see the distal end of the TCL during CT release [98]. The TCL's proximal aspect is situated approximately 2 mm proximal to the distal edge of the TCL. While the distance between the distal end of the TCL and the palmar fat pad decreases with finger flexion, the distance between the TCL and the palmar arch or the Palmar Cutaneous Branch of the Median Nerve (PCBMN) is not significantly influenced. When sectioning the TCL from proximal to distal, observing the proximal part of the fat pad becomes a valuable indicator that the distal edge of the TCL is within approximately 2 mm. This observation signals that further dissection beyond this level is unnecessary, helping to prevent injury to the superficial palmar arch or the PCBMN [35].

Figure 3. Illustration of the anatomy of carpal tunnel [133].

The palmar (volar) surface receives partial insertion from the flexor carpi ulnaris (FCU) and palmaris longus (PL) and gives partial origin to all thenar and hypothenar muscles save the abductor digiti minimi. This surface is completely masked by the muscle attachments, giving the impression that it is considerably deeper than surgeons believe. This may persuade surgeons to make a deeper incision to expose the TCL and divide it completely. The PL tendon (if existent) crosses the middle of this area, with a nerve on either side; palmar cutaneous branch of ulnar nerve

(medially) and PCBMN (laterally) [37]. The superficial branch of the radial artery originates just before the radial artery curves around the carpus, passing through or occasionally over the thenar muscles, providing them with a blood supply. This branch may anastomose with the end of the ulnar artery, completing the superficial palmar arch. When present, it appears as a slender and flattened tendon, coursing superficially to the Transverse Carpal Ligament (TCL) and lying medially to the Flexor Carpi Radialis (FCR) tendon. It is partially inserted into the central part of the TCL and extends distally to attach to the proximal part of the Palmar Aponeurosis (PA). Often, it sends a tendinous slip to the thenar muscles. The Median Nerve (MN) lies deep to this tendon; however, in its absence, the nerve is only separated from the skin by a thin layer of subcutaneous fat and deep fascia [127]. The Palmar Cutaneous Branch of the Median Nerve (PCBMN) originates from the MN proximal to the TCL. It penetrates the deep fascia and runs superficially to the TCL, just lateral to the Palmaris Longus (PL) tendon. It then divides into lateral branches that supply the thenar skin, communicating with the lateral cutaneous nerve of the forearm. The medial branches provide the central palmar skin and communicate with the palmar cutaneous branch of the ulnar nerve. Notably, injury to the PCBMN is the most common complication of carpal tunnel surgery, and it has been proposed that the minimally invasive incision made between the superficial palmar arch and the most distal part of the PCBMN in the palmar region constitutes a safe zone for carpal tunnel surgery. The decreased discomfort reported by patients undergoing endoscopic and subcutaneous types of carpal tunnel release may be attributed, in part, to the preservation of the crossing cutaneous nerves during these procedures [68, 82].

The communicating sensory branches are often multiple and typically originate in the proximal forearm, occasionally stemming from the anterior interosseous branch. These branches pass medially between the Flexor Digitorum Superficialis (FDS) and Flexor Digitorum Profundus (FDP), coursing behind the ulnar artery to join the ulnar nerve. This communication plays a role in accounting for unusual muscular innervations in the hand. In the context of an incision for carpal tunnel (CT) release, the Palmar Cutaneous Branch of the Median Nerve (PCBMN) was observed to cross the incision in only one out of 25 fresh frozen cadaveric hands, while its terminal branches were identified at the incision margin in another two specimens [68]. The PCBMN originates from the ulnar nerve near the middle of the forearm, approximately 4.9 cm proximally to the pisiform bone. It then courses distally, just medial, and parallel to the Palmaris Longus (PL) tendon, entering the palm of the hand superficial to the Transverse Carpal Ligament (TCL). In 24 specimens, at least one, often multiple, transverse palmar cutaneous branches were identified, originating approximately 3 mm distally to the pisiform within Guyon's canal. In another 10 specimens out of 25 hands, a nerve of Henle arose about 14.0 cm proximally to the pisiform, traveling with the ulnar neurovascular bundle to the wrist flexion crease [68, 127]. They enter the hand by a groove

between the pisiform (medially) and the hook of hamate (laterally and more distally) after passing superficially to the FR. The ulnar artery runs radially to the nerve and can be felt on the ulnar side of the wrist. They typically pass just over the ulnar to the superior portion of the hamate's hook. They are held in position over the FR by a fascial extension of the volar carpal ligament, which forms the ulnar canal (Guyon's canal). This extension is linked to the pisiform bone medially and blends laterally with the TCL [37]. They are in the protection of the lateral edge of the FCU tendon [127]. The pisiform bone is palpated near the base of the hypothenar eminence and serves to highlight the ulnar nerve and artery's lateral entry into the hand. The average distance between the radial aspect of the pisiform and the radial border of Guyon's canal and the ulnar edge of the PL tendon is approximately 10.3 mm and 16.1 mm, respectively. The ulnar nerve divides into superficial and deep branches when it travels between the pisiform and hook of hamate [113]. When the wrist is in a neutral position, a looped ulnar artery is situated approximately 2-7 mm medially to 1-4 mm laterally to the hook of the hamate, continuing to form the superficial palmar arch. During radial deviation of the wrist, the looped ulnar artery migrates to the ulnar side of Guyon's canal, positioned approximately 2-3mm radially to the hook of the hamate. In ulnar deviation, the ulnar artery shifts more laterally beyond the hook of the hamate, about 2-7 mm. To minimize postoperative bleeding and avoid iatrogenic ulnar vascular and neural injury, it is recommended to: (1) transect the Transverse Carpal Ligament (TCL) over 4-5 mm apart from the lateral margin of the hook of the hamate without directing the scalpel's edge toward the ulnar side; (2) avoid transecting the TCL in the ulnar deviation wrist position; and (3) create the proximal portal just medial to the Palmaris Longus (PL) tendon to spare the ulnar neurovascular structures. However, ulnar artery injury within Guyon's canal has not been problematic during Endoscopic Carpal Tunnel Release (ECTR) surgery [98]. Variations include an anomaly of the ulnar nerve with an aberrant branch crossing the CT incision and a small arterial branch (average diameter, 0.7 mm) arising from the ulnar artery, running transversely just over the TCL in 6 out of the 24 specimens. This branch consistently located within 15 mm proximally to the TCL distal margin. [49, 76]. The deep surface of the Transverse Carpal Ligament (TCL) forms the carpal tunnel (CT) along with the carpal bones. Within this tunnel, nine flexor tendons of the fingers, their flexor synovial sheaths, and the median nerve traverse. The median nerve, characterized as the softest and most volar structure in the CT, has an average cross-sectional area of 6.19 mm². Positioned directly beneath the TCL, it lies superficial to the nine digital flexor tendons (refer to figure 3). Proximal to the TCL, the median nerve is situated just laterally to the tendons of Flexor Digitorum Superficialis (FDS) and between the tendons of Flexor Carpi Radialis (FCR) and Palmaris Longus (PL) (figure 3). Its location extends an average of 11 mm radially to the hook of the hamate [79]. Distally to the TCL, the median nerve enlarges and flattens, typically dividing into five or six

branches: the recurrent motor branch, three proper digital nerves (two to the thumb and one to the radial side of the index finger), and two common digital nerves (one to the index/middle and one to the middle/ring). In cases of nerve entrapment or compression, the slowed conduction speed at the problematic site, attributed to demyelination, serves as a valuable electrical diagnostic feature [50, 74]. Irregularities in the median nerve (MN): Approximately 11% of the examined specimens exhibited variations in the MN at the wrist. Commonly arising from the medial aspect of the MN, these neural variations pose a potential risk of iatrogenic injury during endoscopic or open release procedures [14]. A study involving 246 carpal tunnels during surgery identified four groups of variations: 12% exhibited variations in the course of the MN, 7% had accessory branches at the distal portion of the carpal tunnel (CT), 3% showed high divisions of the MN, and 1.5% had accessory branches proximal to the carpal canal. These findings underscore the significance of approaching the MN from the ulnar side when accessing the CT [59]. The Persistent Median Artery is a condition, The median artery is a transient vessel representing the embryological axial artery of the forearm, typically regressing in the second fetal month [97]. Its persistence in the human adult manifests in two types: a large, extended vessel reaching the hand (palmar type) or a smaller, shorter vessel ending before reaching the wrist joint (antebrachial type) [109, 111]. This persistence is documented in approximately 3.4% to 20% of a sampled population of 646 hands. More prevalent in females, it tends to occur unilaterally, slightly favoring the right side. Often originating from the caudal angle between the ulnar artery and its common interosseous trunk, the median artery may also arise from the ulnar artery or common interosseous trunk. It typically terminates as the 1st, 2nd, or 1st and 2nd common digital arteries (65%) or joins the superficial palmar arch (35%). In 41% of cases with the palmar type, it pierces the median nerve in the upper third of the forearm. When in its palmar type, the median artery runs under the flexor retinaculum, traveling within the carpal tunnel alongside the median nerve and flexor tendons. This relationship has been suggested as a potential etiological factor in carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) [111]. In 3% of hands (of 110 in surgeries), an abnormal sensory branch emerging from the ulnar side of the MN and piercing the ulnar margin of the TCL was discovered [59]. Martin-Gruber anastomosis is a motor communication nerve that can cross over from the median to the ulnar nerve in the forearm (motor connections, not sensory). It can go from the MN in the proximal forearm to the ulnar nerve in the middle to distal part of the forearm, or from the anterior interosseous nerve to the ulnar nerve [37]. Additional motor anastomoses between the MN and ulnar nerve include: (1) the MN's motor branch to the superficial head of the flexor pollicis brevis (FPB) and the ulnar nerve to the deep head of the FPB; (2) the MN and ulnar motor branches through the first lumbrical or by innervating the adductor pollicis muscle; (3) the MN's branch to the third lumbrical joining neural branch to this muscle from deep branch of the ulnar nerve; (4) the MN may also form anastomoses with a

branch of the radial nerve near the abductor pollicis brevis, which is innervated by the radial nerve; and (5) the MN may be innervated in addition to the adductor pollicis or even the abductor digiti minimi [37]. Recurrent or thenar branch of the motor. It is a small, thick branch that typically emerges from the MN's radial side. However, it could originate from the MN's ulnar or volar sides [98]. It can be the initial Pal-Mar branch or a terminal branch that connects to Minnesota's digital branches. It passes beneath the portion of the PA covering the thenar muscles and runs laterally, just distal to the TCL, with a small recurring curve. It passes either superficially to the muscle or through it after circling the distal edge of the TCL to lie superficially to the FPB, which it typically supplies. It branches into the abductor pollicis brevis, which penetrates the muscle's medial edge and travels deep within it to supply the opponens pollicis, which also pierces the muscle's medial edge. Occasionally, the first dorsal interneural, which may be its only or partial innervation, receives a branch from its terminal part. It could appear in the CT and pierce the TCL, which is a crucial surgical location [127]. Of 116 fresh frozen cadaveric hands, the motor branch's location (in 30 hands) was transligamentous in 6%–23%, subligamentous in 31%–34%, and extra ligamentous in 46%–60% [82]. Thus, the motor branch's most prevalent pattern is extra ligamentous and recurrent. This branch and the distal margin of the TCL are separated by an average of 2.7–6.5 mm [37, 114]. The four tendons of the FDS, four tendons of the FDP, and the tendon of the FPL are the flexor tendons. The tendons of the middle and ring fingers are superficially located above the tendons of the index and little fingers, and the superficialis tendons are all distinct. The tendons of FDS are superficially connected to the MN. Compared to the FDS tendons, the profundus tendons are still deeper. The other three are still fused and lie medially to the index slip; only the slip to the index finger is separate [37]. The TCL's two laminae and the trapezium groove are separated by a unique canal that the FPL tendon travels through radially. It is encircled by a distinct synovial sheath known as the "radial bursa," which runs the length of the thumb to the point where the tendon inserts at the base of the distal phalanx. The radial bursa extends 2.5 cm above the wrist joint/TC in a proximal direction. It may be missing or affixed to the base of the second metacarpal [127].

The palmar fascia, constituting the deep fascia of the palm, exhibits varying thickness over the thenar and hypothenar eminences, with its central part, known as the palmar aponeurosis (PA), being notably robust and triangular. The apex of the PA seamlessly connects proximally with the distal border of the transverse carpal ligament (TCL) and receives the expanded tendon of the palmaris longus (PL). Its base then divides into four slips, each designated for an individual finger. Encompassing the central compartment of the hand, the PA envelops the long flexor tendons and their synovial sheaths, lumbricals, the superficial palmar arch, as well as branches of the median and ulnar nerves with their associated digital nerves and vessels. Within the palm, between the

flexor tendons and the fascia covering the deep palmar muscles, lies the medial central palmar (mid-palmar) space, which maintains continuity with the space in the distal forearm in front of the pronator quadratus (Space of Parona) through the carpal tunnel. The deeper segment of each slip further subdivides into two processes that insert into the fibrous sheaths of the flexor tendons. At these division points, robust transverse fascicular fibers of the PA are strategically positioned along the proximal margin of the flexor tendon sheath. These fibers not only bind the distinct processes together but also anchor to the underlying transverse metacarpal ligament via vertical septa. This configuration forms a protective tunnel around the flexor tendon, serving as a pulley for the flexor tendons, complementing the first and second annular pulleys of the digital flexor mechanism. The significance of the palmar aponeurosis (PA) pulley is comparable to that of the annular and cruciate flexor tendon pulleys [91]. Functionally, the PA plays a crucial role in mitigating the tendency of the flexor tendons to bowstring around the metacarpophalangeal joint, especially in conjunction with the proximal annular pulleys. Structurally, the PA constitutes a fibro tendinous complex that serves as both a tendinous extension when the palmaris longus (PL) is present and a robust stabilizing structure for the palmar skin of the hand. The PA encompasses a deeper transverse portion that traverses the palm at the proximal ends of the metacarpal bones. This aponeurosis provides a secure attachment to the overlying skin, contributes to the formation of palm ridges, enhancing friction for a firm grip on objects. Additionally, it acts as a protective layer for underlying structures and serves as an attachment point for muscles. The transverse fascicular fibers of the PA at the proximal margin of the flexor tendon sheath function as a pulley, further emphasizing its pivotal role in hand biomechanics [91]. Throughout their trajectory, the long flexor tendons navigate a complex pulley system, comprising the TCL, PA, and digital pulleys. Within this system, the synovial fluid acts as a lubricant, ensuring minimal friction between the tendons and pulleys. In vivo, during active flexion and extension of the wrist and fingers, measurements indicate that the longitudinal excursion of the tendons ranges from 24 to 50 mm, while the median nerve (MN) exhibits an excursion of 11 to 28 mm during wrist and elbow movements. Notably, non-inflammatory fibrosis and thickening of the synovium are identified as primary contributors to MN compression [106]. These synovial alterations impact the gliding characteristics of the sub synovial connective tissue (SSCT), causing it to move synchronously with the tendons and MN. This phenomenon is implicated in the etiology of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS). A significant majority (approximately 90%) of synovial specimens obtained from individuals with idiopathic CTS do not display inflammatory changes but rather exhibit edema or fibrosis. Chronic synovial degeneration is further evidenced by increased fibroblast density, collagen fiber size, and vascular proliferation [106, 120]. Furthermore, the flexor tendons undergo volar displacement from the floor of the carpal tunnel during active finger movement. This displacement generates a

compressive force and reaction between the tendons and the TCL. The force applied to the TCL during finger movement is nearly equivalent to the force exerted by the flexor tendons [112].

1.5 Clinical diagnosis of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome

1.5.1 Stages of CTS

The symptoms and signs of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) can be classified into three distinct stages (table 1). In the initial stage, individuals wake up from sleep with a sensation of numbness or swelling in the hand, despite no visible swelling. They may experience intense pain radiating from the wrist to the shoulder, accompanied by tingling in the hand and fingers, known as brachialgia paresthetica nocturna. Shaking or flicking the hand often provides relief, but the hand may feel stiff in the morning.

Table 1. Classification of carpal tunnel syndrome according to severity [41].

Classification	Duration of symptoms	Weakness/Atrophy	Electrodiagnostic results
Mild	Less than 1 year	None present	Abnormal sensory nerve conduction velocity, normal distal motor latency
Moderate	Less/greater than 1 year	Minimal present	Abnormal sensory nerve conduction velocity; abnormal distal motor latency
Severe	Greater than 1 year	Marked weakness/atrophy	Abnormal (or absent) sensory nerve conduction velocity; abnormal (or absent) distal motor latency

The second stage involves the manifestation of symptoms during the day, particularly during repetitive hand or wrist movements or prolonged periods in the same position. Patients may notice clumsiness when gripping objects, leading to objects slipping from their hands. The third and final

stage is characterized by hypotrophy or atrophy of the thenar eminence, and at this point, sensory symptoms may no longer be felt [41, 74].

1.5.2 Assessment of CTS

When diagnosing a patient with CTS, it is crucial to gather a comprehensive case history related to the characteristic signs of CTS. Questions should focus on whether symptoms predominantly occur at night or during the day, if specific positions or repetitive movements trigger symptoms, whether vibratory instruments are used at work, and the specific areas where symptoms are felt (hand, wrist, or shoulder). Inquiring about alleviating measures, such as shaking or flicking, and identifying any predisposing factors is also essential. Various factors, including inflammatory arthritis, diabetes mellitus, pregnancy, hypothyroidism, Colle's' fracture, acromegaly, amyloidosis, adiposity, myxedema, chronic polyarthritis, or the use of corticosteroids and estrogens, may be linked to CTS [5, 56]. Since certain physical findings may point to the existence of other disorders, a thorough physical examination of the patient's hand and wrist is crucial to the diagnosis of CTS. On the hands and wrists, abrasions or ecchymosis may be signs of tissue damage, which may also involve damage to the median nerve. It may be determined that a patient has rheumatoid arthritis if skeletal anomalies such as the boutonniere deformity, swan neck deformity, or ulnar deviation of the wrist are discovered. Should bossing be felt on the distal phalanx or carpal bones, osteoarthritis could be the reason [122, 129]. In the diagnostic process for carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), patient history and physical examination offer limited insights into specific symptom occurrences. To enhance the assessment, tools like the Katz Hand Diagram come into play, enabling patients to detail the location and nature of symptoms whether its numbness, pain, tingling, or hypoesthesia. The completed diagram categorizes symptoms into potential patterns: classical, probable/possible, possible, or unlikely. The classical pattern involves symptoms in at least two of the first, second, or third fingers, potentially extending to the fourth and fifth fingers, along with wrist pain and radiation proximally to the wrist, excluding the palm or dorsum. A probable diagram indicates the presence of CTS with 64% sensitivity and 73% specificity. The flick sign, a subjective test where patients report symptom relief with flicking or shaking at night (sensitivity = 93%, specificity = 96%), can further indicate CTS. Traditional provocative tests, like Phalen's test (sensitivity = 57%-91%, specificity = 33%-86%), involve specific wrist movements. These diagnostic approaches provide a more comprehensive understanding of CTS symptoms and aid in accurate identification[6]. It is also feasible to do the "reverse Phalen's test" (sensitivity = 57%; specificity = 78%) [65], often referred to as the "Wormer's test" or wrist extension test [134] in which the patient voluntarily extends their wrist

and fingers for two minutes. Additional diagnostic tests for carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) include Tinel's sign, where the physician taps along the median nerve near the carpal tunnel, and Durkan's test, also known as carpal compression, involving the compression of the median nerve at the carpal ligament's proximal edge. The hand elevation test requires the patient to raise both arms, elbows, and shoulders, holding the position for up to two minutes, and the tourniquet test, or Gillet test, involves raising a blood pressure cuff on the patient's arm to the systolic blood pressure level. If paresthesia develops or increases in the median nerve distribution within one minute or less during these tests, they are considered positive for CTS suspicion. Despite their simplicity and low cost, these provocative tests and physical examinations lack diagnostic value and predictive accuracy, especially when the likelihood of CTS is low, and their results show no correlation with the severity of CTS. Therefore, cautious interpretation is necessary when relying on these methods for diagnostic conclusions [54, 95].

The physician should gather a comprehensive patient history by addressing various aspects related to hand numbness, wrist pain, and associated symptoms. Firstly, inquire about the duration of symptoms and their severity, including when they occur, such as at night. Explore the character of symptoms, considering descriptors like tingling, burning, or aching, and determine if numbness or tingling is intermittent or persistent. Investigate factors that alleviate or worsen symptoms, such as activities like driving or tool use. Identify the location and radiation of pain and numbness, specifically in the median nerve distribution of the hand(s) and assess for any associated symptoms in other body areas. Understand the pace of illness, whether it is improving, worsening, or remaining stable, and inquire about the rate of change if applicable [1]. Document any previous treatments and their effectiveness, including splints, injections, therapy, or medications. Lastly, explore the patient's lifestyle, including common hand-related activities such as hobbies or occupation, and assess for functional limitations resulting from these symptoms. Planning the best course of treatment and making a diagnosis of CTS are aided by obtaining a history of the condition. The literature does not currently have enough evidence to evaluate the diagnostic utility of history data or its predictive value in assessing illness severity and treatment outcomes. To help doctors ask the right questions during patient interactions to improve diagnosis, the work group consulted experts to create this proposal [9]. The literature is conflicting about whether the length of symptoms indicates the severity of nerve damage or whether it may be used to forecast how well a treatment will work. Furthermore, it's uncertain if the nature and intensity of the symptoms are connected to the anatomical and physiological state of the median nerve. Across all trials (regardless of design) or when examining findings for a particular electrodiagnostic test, the evidence from the research that are now available does not show a direct correlation between symptoms and the outcomes of these tests. Classic symptoms that when combined may be highly

diagnostic of CTS include numbness along the median nerve's distribution, worsening of symptoms at night when sleeping, relief of symptoms by shaking the hand, and exacerbation of symptoms when driving or holding a phone [51].

The identification of symptom location and radiation is crucial for distinguishing between conditions like proximal nerve compression syndrome that may mimic CTS, either excluding or including such diagnoses. The presence of associated symptoms serves as an important indicator for physicians to consider alternative diagnoses beyond CTS. CTS symptoms may exhibit variability daily, and understanding this fluctuation is valuable for determining an appropriate diagnosis and treatment strategy. In cases where symptoms fluctuate periodically without a progressive increase in severity, conservative management may be considered for diagnostic purposes. Evaluating the patient's response to previous treatments can serve as confirmation of the CTS diagnosis and support the decision to proceed with carpal tunnel surgery [51]. Responses to conservative treatments can vary, with the most significant improvement observed around 1 month after steroid injections and between 3 and 6 months when using electrodiagnostic tests to measure changes in distal motor latency. The physician should conduct a thorough physical examination encompassing various aspects [123]. This examination involves assessing personal characteristics such as age, sex, weight, height, and body habitus. Additionally, the range of motion in the hand and wrist should be evaluated, and any observed deformities, swelling, atrophy, or skin trophic changes should be noted. The assessment should include tests for pinch and grip strength, utilizing a hand diagram to pinpoint the location of symptoms. Sensory examination, involving techniques like two-point discrimination, Semmes-Weinstein monofilament testing, vibrometry, and texture discrimination, is essential. Manual muscle testing of the upper extremity is crucial to identify any muscular atrophy, particularly in the thenar muscle group. Provocative tests, including the Phalen test, Tinel sign, median nerve compression test, and reverse Phalen test, should be performed. Additionally, a discriminatory examination for alternative diagnoses, such as radiculopathy, neuropathy, pain syndromes, arthritis, tendinitis, and vascular abnormalities, is integral to ensure a comprehensive evaluation [123].

Essential information for the evaluation and management documentation includes basic personal characteristics such as age, sex, height, weight, and body habitus. This evaluation encompasses the determination of vascular status, identification of obvious deformities, and testing for other related conditions like basilar thumb arthritis, de Quervain disease, cubital tunnel syndrome, and cervical radiculopathy. Sensory examination, utilizing methods like two-point discrimination, Semmes-Weinstein monofilament, vibrometry, and texture discrimination, is crucial for defining the anatomic distribution of sensory changes. However, the existing literature lacks adequate evidence to recommend one test over another or to establish the overall utility of

these tests in diagnosing carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) [1]. Future research is needed to confirm the diagnostic efficacy of these sensory tests. Manual muscle testing of the upper extremity, particularly assessing for apparent muscle atrophy, is significant, with a specific focus on the thenar muscle area [9]. Although thenar atrophy is reported to have a high predictive value in CTS, its occurrence is infrequent, and the limited available studies do not allow for a conclusive determination of its diagnostic value. In the evaluation and diagnosis of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), several provocative tests are considered, although no single test has been established as the gold standard due to various reasons such as poor study design, inconsistent data, and limited research on the same tests [58]. The sensitivity and specificity of the Phalen test ranged from 0.46 to 0.80 and 0.51 to 0.91, respectively. Similarly, the Tinel sign showed sensitivity ranging from 0.28 to 0.73 and specificity from 0.44 to 0.95, while the median nerve compression test exhibited sensitivity between 0.04 and 0.79 and specificity between 0.25 and 0.96 [55]. Combining results from multiple provocative tests may enhance sensitivity and specificity, as demonstrated by the Phalen and median nerve compression tests with a sensitivity of 0.92 and a specificity of 0.92 [135]. However, further research is needed to confirm the diagnostic accuracy of this combined approach. Tests like the reverse Phalen test, tethered median nerve stress test, and the tourniquet test have limited evaluations, and conclusive evidence regarding their accuracy in CTS diagnosis is currently insufficient [38]. While carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) diagnosis cannot solely rely on clinical or electrodiagnostic criteria, evidence suggests that a combination of both approaches can enhance diagnostic confirmation and guide treatment decisions, particularly regarding carpal tunnel release. However, the specific combination tests vary significantly across studies. For instance:

- Haupt employed motor and sensory tests in combination with distal motor latency of the median nerve, antidromic sensory nerve conduction velocity (NCV), and electromyography (EMG) examination of abductor pollicis brevis [43].
- Braun and Jackson utilized a combination of range of motion, grip strength, pinch strength, monofilament sensory evaluation, Phalen, and Tinel tests along with sensory latency exceeding 3.5 ms [19].
- Glowacki employed either Phalen or Tinel tests in conjunction with motor latencies exceeding 4.0 ms, sensory latencies surpassing 3.7 ms, amplitudes below 20 μ V, or a conduction velocity below 50 m/s with evidence of fibrillation [28].
- Boniface incorporated sensory tests along with prolonged median sensory conduction velocity and distal motor latency to abductor pollicis brevis [17].

Despite these examples, the limited number of studies in these diagnostic groupings prevents the identification of definitive combinations of clinical and electrodiagnostic tests that exhibit optimal

performance. Future research should focus on comparing the diagnostic accuracy of various test combinations to pinpoint and recommend specific combinations for enhanced diagnostic efficacy.

Symptoms resembling those of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) may also be indicative of other conditions, such as cervical radiculopathy, hypothyroidism, peripheral neuropathy, wrist/trapeziometacarpal arthrosis, wrist tendinitis/tenosynovitis, Raynaud disease, arterial injury or thrombosis, nerve laceration, neuroma, brachial plexus injury, and various pain syndromes. In conducting a physical examination, it is crucial to explore areas beyond the carpal tunnel that may be relevant to these alternative diagnoses [67]. This includes assessing muscular atrophy or weakness in the shoulder, elbow, wrist, thumb, and/or fingers, active range of motion with particular emphasis on the wrist and digits, the presence of swelling, masses, and/or tenderness around the wrist or digits, evaluation of capillary refill, radial and ulnar pulses, and the Allen test, inspection for wounds or scars on the upper extremity, examination of cervical spine range of motion, consideration of the Spurling sign, assessment for thyroid enlargement, and utilization of wrist radiographs [123]. By examining these additional aspects, healthcare professionals can rule out or identify other potential conditions that may manifest with symptoms resembling CTS. Physicians may opt for electrodiagnostic tests to discern between various diagnoses, particularly considering such tests in cases involving thenar atrophy and/or persistent numbness [92]. Despite these limitations, experts suggest that, in certain instances, nerve conduction velocity (NCV) studies and needle electromyography (EMG) can aid in distinguishing CTS from other peripheral nerve problems such as polyneuropathy, brachial plexopathy, or cervical radiculopathy [67]. Moreover, the presence of thenar atrophy and/or persistent numbness may indicate severe nerve injury, warranting more proactive management or diagnostic evaluation, with NCV studies and EMG serving to document such severe nerve injury. If clinical and/or provocative tests yield positive results and surgical intervention is under consideration, the physician should request electrodiagnostic tests [67]. A clinically relevant reference standard for assessing patient care and management is the improvement in symptoms following surgical release. Several studies have identified a correlation between a combination of clinical presentation (symptoms and either the Phalen test or Tinel sign) and nerve conduction studies, demonstrating a favorable surgical outcome [92]. The meta-regression of surgical outcome and clinical/electrodiagnostic tests further supports this correlation. Notably, the association with clinical tests alone or electrodiagnostic tests alone did not exhibit a statistically significant connection with surgical outcomes. High-quality studies investigating the correlation between outcomes of alternative treatments (e.g., splinting, steroid injections) and pretreatment diagnostic results were lacking [71]. While a positive response to surgery doesn't confirm the diagnosis of CTS, as other factors like placebo effects, activity

modification, and postoperative splinting can contribute to symptom relief, postsurgical improvement remains a relevant measure in assessing patient outcomes [67].

1.5.3 Nerve conduction studies

Nerve conduction studies are often considered a gold standard for defining carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS). This objective test provides insights into the physiological health of the median nerve as it traverses the carpal tunnel. The diagnostic criterion involves comparing the focal median nerve function across the wrist with another section of the nerve, typically within the same hand. During the test, the nerve receives transcutaneous electrical stimulation, generating an action potential, and a recording electrode (placed either distally or proximally) captures the wave of depolarization. The recorded latency and amplitude of the signal is crucial parameters. The electrodiagnostic technique's effectiveness in confirming CTS diagnosis lies in testing the median nerve fiber across the wrist and comparing the latency (and occasionally amplitude) to normal conduction or comparing it to another nerve segment in the same hand that bypasses the carpal tunnel (such as the median, ulnar, or radial nerves). Numerous studies highlight that comparing sensory nerve responses is more sensitive than relying solely on absolute median latency to identify electrodiagnostic abnormalities consistent with CTS [2]. The vibratory threshold has been proposed as an initial objective indicator in individuals with carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), stemming from controlled experiments involving external pressure on the carpal canal. These studies demonstrated a close correlation between the vibratory threshold and both subjective changes in sensation and the loss of sensory nerve response [15]. While vibratory thresholds have proven useful in assessing individuals with generalized peripheral polyneuropathies, such as diabetes, uremia, or drug-induced neuropathy, their role in evaluating CTS remains less defined. Criteria for aiding in the diagnosis vary, with some using absolute threshold criteria, and others suggesting comparisons between different digits. Although both nerve conduction studies (NCS) and vibrometry examine large, myelinated fibers in the median nerve, their correlations have been relatively low. NCS can detect nerve slowing, a primary process in CTS involving the loss of myelin insulation, with mild cases exhibiting slowing of conduction without axon loss [39]. Vibrometry, on the other hand, has limited utility in screening for CTS. Another testing approach is current perception threshold (CPT) testing, which assesses an individual's perception of electrical current at three frequencies. However, studies indicate that CPT testing has low sensitivity, specificity, and positive predictive values for identifying subjects with median nerve function slowing or CTS symptoms. Symptom surveys, hand diagrams, physical examinations, and quantitative sensory testing (Semmes–Weinstein monofilaments, two-point discrimination,

tactile sensation) are additional diagnostic tools. While hand diagrams have shown high sensitivity and specificity in clinical settings, their efficacy as screening tools in industrial settings is unclear.

Physical examinations and quantitative sensory testing exhibit low sensitivity, with variability in testing procedures posing reliability challenges. Two-point discrimination is limited to more severe CTS cases [136]. Several studies, including those by Bingham [137], Franzblau, indicate that approximately 15% of the general population may display evidence of a median mononeuropathy without reporting hand symptoms [31]. This phenomenon is not exclusive to the general population, as diabetics often exhibit abnormal median nerve conditions across the wrist without reporting symptoms[4]. These findings challenge the specificity commonly reported in convenience samples, which typically ranges from 97% to 99% [2, 4]. The question arises whether individuals with evidence of a median mononeuropathy without symptoms represent pre-clinical cases of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), indicating a diseased nerve that has yet to manifest symptoms but may do so in the future. Werner addressed this question through a case-control study involving active workers at multiple sites [119]. Cases were defined as asymptomatic workers with electrodiagnostic findings of a median mononeuropathy, while controls were age- and sex-matched asymptomatic workers with normal nerve conduction studies (NCS). The study found that NCS were not useful in determining the risk of developing CTS within the first two years. Asymptomatic workers with an abnormal median sensory evoked response did not exhibit a higher likelihood of developing CTS symptoms than those with a normal median sensory nerve conduction during the initial two years. However, after a total of six years, an association between a median mononeuropathy and future CTS symptoms emerged. The risk of developing CTS symptoms increased with the severity of the baseline abnormality in median nerve function, consistent with similar findings in the study by Nathan [138]. In both studies, approximately 25% of asymptomatic workers with a median mononeuropathy went on to develop CTS symptoms after 6–11 years, with the majority of those with an abnormal median sensory latency at baseline not developing CTS symptoms.

1.5.4 Imaging studies

Conventional radiography has a limited utility in the primary diagnosis of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) as it cannot visualize the soft tissue component of the carpal tunnel. However, it may be valuable in cases associated with bony stenosis, fractures, and soft tissue calcification. Therefore, its use should be considered only when there is a history of hand trauma or restrictions in wrist movement [16]. Computed tomography (CT) scanning presents a potentially superior alternative to plain radiography for a clear depiction of the bony structures within the carpal tunnel. CT scans can effectively reveal unusual bony formations and structures occupying the carpal

tunnel space that may not be evident through external examination (figure.3). Nevertheless, nerve compression is not distinctly visible unless related to a bony condition [16]. Some reports indicate a limited contribution of CT scanning in primary CTS cases [70, 100]. In summary, both plain radiography and CT scans have minor roles in the diagnosis of CTS, and their application is challenging to standardize due to inherent limitations in assessing soft tissue changes. Therefore, routine use of CT scans and plain radiography for CTS diagnosis is not recommended unless there is suspicion of hard tissue-related changes such as bone fracture, osseous carpal stenosis, or soft tissue calcification. With recent advancements in ultrasound imaging resolution, high-quality images of peripheral nerves and fascia can now be obtained. Ultrasonography (US) has proven effective in detecting changes in the flexor retinaculum, as well as perineural and intraneural vascularization of the median nerve in idiopathic carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS).

Figure 3. An axial computed tomography (CT) scan reveals the bony section of the carpal tunnel at the outlet level. The sequence of bony structures from left to right includes the HAMATE, CAPITATE, TRAPEZOID, and TRAPEZIUM. The flexor retinaculum (FR), and flexor tendons are seen here through the CT scan [37].

A study conducted by Nakamichi and Tachibana, involving 414 symptomatic wrists and 408 control wrists, compared sonography and nerve conduction study results [75]. Measurements of the cross-sectional area (CSA) of the median nerve at the distal edge of the flexor retinaculum, the hook of hamate, and the pisiform revealed clear differences between symptomatic and control patients. Proposed cutoff values for CSA at these levels ranged from an average of 12 mm² to 13, 11, and 14 mm², demonstrating specificity greater than 95% and sensitivity ranging from 43% to 57%. Another study by El Miedany [73] measured CSA at the carpal tunnel inlet, showing higher sensitivity and specificity than Nakamichi and Tachibana. With 96 symptomatic wrists and 156 control wrists, the study established cutoffs for mild, moderate, and severe disease at 10 mm², 13

mm², and 15 mm², respectively, achieving sensitivities and specificities of 98% and 100%, 98% and 97%, and 97% and 99%. While axial CT scans are effective in regularly identifying the flexor tendons of the fingers, the resolution is not adequate for assessing soft tissue changes within the carpal tunnel [110]. Nonetheless, CT provides several notable advantages over plain radiographs. It allows for precise determination of the etiology, localization, and extent of osseous carpal stenosis through axial thin-section images and multiplanar or three-dimensional reconstructed images. CT is also more adept at detecting soft tissue calcifications and space-occupying lesions within the carpal tunnel. However, in cases involving non-calcified lesions, CT is considered inferior to MR imaging [53].

Figure 4. Ultrasonography of the proximal carpal tunnel reveals specific anatomical structures: arrowheads denote the flexor retinaculum, while FCR represents the flexor carpi radialis tendon, FPL corresponds to the flexor pollicis longus tendon, and MN signifies the median nerve. Additionally, T is used to indicate the flexor digitorum superficialis and profundus tendons [52].

Ultrasound is advantageous over nerve conduction studies as it can exclude other conditions with CTS-like symptoms, such as tenosynovitis, mass lesions, and anatomical defects. Its cost-effectiveness, accessibility, noninvasiveness, and short examination time make it a recommended first-line diagnostic tool for CTS. In more complex cases requiring confirmation, ultrasound's greater sensitivity and less invasiveness position it as a valuable tool compared to nerve conduction studies [110]. While a reliable diagnostic standard for CTS is yet to be established, studies suggest that ultrasound can rule out CTS if the median nerve CSA in the carpal tunnel inlet is below 10 mm² [53]. Additional ultrasound measurements (figure 5), such as flexor retinaculum bowing,

flattening of the median nerve, and decreased longitudinal excursion, offer supplementary information but are considered less reliable.

Figure 5. Ultrasonography of the distal carpal tunnel provides a detailed view of specific structures: H denotes the hamate, MN represents the median nerve, arrowheads indicate the flexor retinaculum, T corresponds to the flexor digitorum superficialis and profundus tendons, and TR signifies the trapezium [52].

Ultrasound does have limitations, including axial and lateral resolution constraints of the transducer and challenges in differentiating the median nerve from surrounding structures, particularly in the distal carpal tunnel. Universal implementation of ultrasound with a standardized protocol is feasible due to the reproducibility of measurements [11]. MRI, owing to its superior spatial resolution, can identify morphological alterations in the median nerve associated with carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS). Common abnormalities observed in CTS patients through MRI include increased signal intensity on T2-weighted images (figure 6), changes in the cross-sectional area (CSA), and flattening of the median nerve [11]. However, the drawbacks of MRI encompass its expense, limited availability, potential for inducing claustrophobia, lengthy scan times, and contraindications in individuals with cardiac pacemakers or specific metallic implants.

Both ultrasonography and MRI share identical imaging criteria for CTS detection, involving:

1. Swelling of the median nerve, assessable at different levels within the carpal tunnel.
2. Flattening ratio (FR), typically indicating proximal swelling and distal flattening of the median nerve, measured quantitatively.
3. Palmer bowing of the flexor retinaculum, a consequence of increased pressure within the carpal tunnel.

Figure 6. In the axial T1-weighted image of the carpal tunnel at the tunnel outlet level, the bony section of the carpal tunnel exhibits intermediate signal intensity, consisting of left to right of the hamate, capitate, trapezoid, and trapezium. The hook of the hamate is indicated by the black arrow, the median nerve by the yellow arrow, and the flexor retinaculum by the green arrow [37].

Ultrasound presents advantages over MRI due to its cost-effectiveness, portability, real-time and dynamic imaging capabilities, and the ability to scan extremities swiftly and efficiently [11]. Furthermore, ultrasound can be employed in patients ineligible for MRI, and any identified abnormal findings can be readily compared with the opposite side.

2. CURRENT TREATMENT MODALITIES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS IN MANAGEMENT

2.1 Non-surgical management of CTS

There are two types of CTS treatment: surgical and non-surgical. Standard open carpal tunnel release, endoscopic carpal tunnel release, open carpal tunnel release in conjunction with procedures, and open carpal tunnel release employing a variety of incision techniques are among the surgical therapies available. A greater variety of options are available for non-surgical treatment, also known as conservative treatment, including splinting, injections of cortical steroids, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, vitamin B6, diuretics, ultrasound therapy, ergonomic positioning, manual therapy intervention, lidocaine patches, and acupuncture. The intensity of the symptoms is what determines how to treat carpal tunnel syndrome [51]. Treatments other than surgery are advised for individuals with moderate CTS symptoms. It is advised that patients with moderate to severe symptoms get evaluated surgically. Before exploring various treatment options, it is crucial to assess the outcomes in comparison to the alternative of no intervention. The decision for early surgical intervention often stems from the belief that the condition progresses, and that delayed treatment may yield less favorable results [51]. However, there is a notable absence of robust evidence concerning the untreated natural progression of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS). The most comprehensive study addressing this issue is conducted by Padua, involving 441 hands affected by idiopathic CTS [85]. The findings reveal that 21% of the hands demonstrated improvement over a 10–15-month follow-up period without active intervention. It is noteworthy that 68% of the patients made efforts to reduce hand stress related to occupation and recreation, and 32% altered either their hobby or work [85]. Predictors of better outcomes included a shorter history, younger age, unilateral symptoms, and a negative Phalen sign. While this study focused on a selected sample of patients, excluding those requiring immediate surgery, it provides the most reliable estimate available for the natural remission rate of CTS. Any therapeutic intervention should aim for an improvement rate surpassing the observed 21% [85]. Commonly employed treatments for carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) have seen minimal changes over the years. These include: (1) immobilizing the hand with splints in a neutral position; (2) administering steroid injections just proximal to and within the carpal tunnel; and (3) decompressing the median nerve through the release of the transverse carpal ligament.

Non-invasive methods are essential in the total treatment of CTS, including conservative options that aim to relieve symptoms, improve functional ability, and enhance the overall quality of life for those with the condition. To fully comprehend the complex nature of CTS, it is essential

to thoroughly examine conservative therapy, taking into account the various elements that contribute to the symptoms. This thesis seeks to clarify the present state of non-surgical treatments for carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), including wrist splinting, physical therapy, pharmaceutical interventions, and alternative therapies. Through a rigorous analysis of the data, practical implementations, and patient results linked to each modality, our aim is to provide significant insights to the wider domain of musculoskeletal health. Given the increasing desire for non-invasive therapies, it is crucial to have a comprehensive knowledge of the many non-surgical therapy alternatives for carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS). This thesis aims to fill the current gap in knowledge by providing a thorough assessment of the several conservative techniques used in the management of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome. The goal is to contribute to informed decision-making in clinical practice.

2.1.1 Non steroid anti-inflammatory drugs

Oral anti-inflammatory medications are commonly prescribed for carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) with the aim of reducing swelling that puts pressure on the median nerve within the carpal tunnel, against the flexor retinaculum [21]. Ibuprofen, at a dosage of 800 mg two to three times daily for one to 10 days, is among the frequently employed oral medications. According to a survey of American Hand Surgeons, oral steroids, diuretics, and NSAIDs are commonly utilized. Another study on primary care treatment for CTS revealed that splints (56.3%) and NSAIDs (50.8%) were the two most administered interventions [139].

2.1.2 Corticosteroid injections

Injecting a long-acting corticosteroid, such as methylprednisolone or betamethasone, into the carpal tunnel is another frequently utilized technique; nevertheless, relapses are common. While a substantial percentage of patients experienced symptom reduction after 2 ± 4 months from corticosteroid injections into the carpal tunnel, only 22% of patients in one research reported no symptoms after 18 months [18]. According to Chang's research (2015), patients with mild to moderate CTS benefited the most from conservative treatment with steroid injection [22]. Lidocaine (control) was compared to methylprednisolone (intervention) and lidocaine (control) by Dammers [26]. At one month, they discovered that 23 patients (77%) in the intervention group had improved compared to six (20%) in the control group. They came to the conclusion that, before undergoing surgical decompression, a single steroid injection near the carpal tunnel may produce long-term benefit.

2.1.3 Splinting

Splinting is a common non-surgical approach for Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS), aiming to alleviate symptoms by immobilizing the wrist in a neutral position, reducing pressure on the median nerve. It provides support during activities that may worsen symptoms, particularly at night when symptoms often peak. Splints can be custom-made or off-the-shelf, but their effectiveness varies depending on individual needs. While splinting can offer relief, it's crucial to consult with a healthcare professional to ensure its suitability and proper usage, often as part of a comprehensive treatment plan that may include exercises and other interventions tailored to the individual's condition. Frequently, splinting is combined with corticosteroid injections but can also be effective as a standalone treatment, although recurrences are common. The cock-up splint (15 degrees from horizontal) and neutral nocturnal wrist supports are the most commonly used types of splints (figure 8).

Figure 8. Wrist neutral splint for carpal tunnel syndrome [81].

Despite its common use, a study investigating the potential effects on intracarpal pressure did not find a significant reduction in pressure in the carpal tunnel compared to controls who did not use splints [63]. In a study by Feuerstein, splinting was associated with more pain and greater strength deficits than simple range of motion exercises. Another study suggested that a higher percentage of patients (83%) reported pain at follow-up when treated with NSAIDs and splinting compared to those receiving splinting and iontophoresis (35%). It's noteworthy that subjects who underwent surgery after a trial of splinting and a steroid injection showed no difference in outcomes compared to subjects receiving the steroid injection/splint intervention without surgery

[29]. Evidence from a different study showed that patients who had NSAIDs and splinting experienced pain at follow-up at a higher rate (83%) than those who received splinting and iontophoresis (35%) [12]. Interestingly, there was no difference in the results of participants who underwent surgery following a trial of splinting and steroid injection compared to those who received the steroid injection/splint intervention without surgery.

2.1.4 Therapeutic ultrasound

Ultrasound, within the intensity range of 0.5 ± 2.0 W/cm², has the potential to induce various biophysical effects within tissue. This treatment is typically administered in either continuous or pulsed mode, with pulsed mode being indicated for acute injuries and continuous mode for chronic injuries. Ultrasound is employed to elevate the temperature in underlying soft tissues, enhance blood flow rates, tissue metabolism, nerve function, the extensibility of connective tissue, and the permeability of biological membranes [83]. For the treatment of CTS, pulsed ultrasound treatment lasts approximately 15 minutes per session over the carpal tunnel area at a frequency of 1 MHz and an intensity of 1.0 W/cm², with a duty cycle of 1:4, a 5 cm transducer, and aqua sonic gel as a couplant. Ultrasound can also be performed continuously with intensities ranging from 0.1 to 2.0 W/cm². In a study by Ebenbichler, the protocol involved comparing pulsed ultrasound treatment to a 'sham' treatment, with sessions occurring five times a week for 2 weeks in the first treatment period and 10 treatments spread over 5 weeks in the second period for both the ultrasound and sham groups. A favorable response rate was noted on a subjective visual analog scale and EMG in 68% of ultrasound-treated patients at the end of both treatment periods, suggesting that ultrasound treatment may be similarly effective to steroid injections and/or wrist splinting. In this study, improvements persisted for at least 6 months in most patients, indicating that ultrasound treatment has good short-term effectiveness and yields satisfying medium-term effects in patients with mild to moderate idiopathic CTS [83].

Studies proposing the stimulation of nerve regeneration, improved nerve conduction, and findings of an anti-inflammatory effect by ultrasound support the concept that ultrasound treatment might facilitate recovery from nerve compression. However, the underlying mechanisms of tissue regeneration by ultrasound remain unclear. Most studies have been conducted in laboratory settings, and few report the benefits of ultrasound treatment in CTS under actual clinical conditions. Oztas found that ultrasound treatment in CTS was only as effective as a placebo in providing symptomatic relief [83].

2.1.5 Manual therapy and high velocity techniques

Manipulating the transverse carpal ligament has proven to be a safe and effective treatment for mild to moderate CTS. Various manipulative techniques are employed because some practitioners believe that these methods can elongate the transverse carpal ligament, alleviating pressure on the median nerve within the carpal tunnel. A study by Sucher revealed MRI-measured increases in both transverse and anteroposterior dimensions of the carpal canal following manipulation and stretching [121]. Manipulative procedures on the upper extremity and spine involve high-velocity, low-force manual thrusts administered to the specified articulation. Sucher and Hinrichs conducted a study on seven cadaver limbs to quantify the elongation of the transverse carpal ligament in response to manipulation, sustained load bearing, or a combination of both [140]. Their findings suggested that manipulations hold promise as a non-surgical approach to relieve pressure on the median nerve in CTS patients. In a study by Davis, NSAIDs and splints were compared to high-velocity, low-amplitude manual thrust procedures that induced a cavitation response and increased joint motion in the bony joints of the upper extremity, including the wrist, elbow, shoulder, as well as the vertebrae of the cervical and upper thoracic regions. The results indicated that both treatment groups enhanced finger sensation and increased nerve conduction velocities, although the time for the response varied considerably [141].

2.1.6 Accupuncture

Originating from Eastern medicine, acupuncture therapy has been globally employed for the treatment of mild to moderate CTS. Acupuncture seeks to activate certain spots along the meridian, a hypothesised channel of energy (qi) throughout the body (figure 9). It is believed that optimising this energy channel can alleviate symptoms of CTS without changing the mechanical pressures inside the carpal tunnel. Although the exact mechanism of action is still unclear, some ideas include that it may have a neuromodulatory influence on pain perception by stimulating the creation of natural pain-relieving substances in the central nervous system and activating pathways that reduce inflammation. Research investigating the efficacy of acupuncture in treating carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) has shown inconclusive findings [142]. Yang and colleagues conducted a comparison between acupuncture needling, consisting of eight sessions over a period of four weeks, and a four-week treatment with oral prednisolone, with a dosage of 20 mg daily for the first two weeks followed by 10 mg for the subsequent two weeks. The study revealed that both therapies were effective in alleviating symptoms. However, the acupuncture group demonstrated

a reduction in nocturnal awakening and decreased distal motor latencies after 4 weeks, in comparison to the steroid group [124].

Figure 9. Accupuncture points for CTS [143].

On the other hand, a randomised controlled trial conducted by Yao and colleagues compared the effects of acupuncture therapy to placebo acupuncture over a period of 6 weeks. The study revealed that both groups showed improvements compared to their initial state, and it was concluded that acupuncture did not show superiority over the placebo treatment [125]. According to a recent Cochrane review that analysed 12 studies including 869 patients, Choi et al. found that acupuncture may not have a significant short-term impact on symptoms of carpal tunnel syndrome when compared to placebo or sham operations. The main reason for this was mostly due to the heterogeneity of the studies and the potential for bias. The authors also noted that the inconsistent reporting of side effects of acupuncture, such as skin bruising and local pain following needle insertion, must be documented in order to thoroughly evaluate the risks and benefits before suggesting treatment [23]. In the future, it will be necessary to conduct further research with enhanced methods to evaluate the role of acupuncture as a standalone treatment approach. These studies should focus on enrollment criteria, indications, and outcomes.

2.1.7 Soft tissue microtrauma therapy

The ASTM AdvantEDGE system, developed by Performance Dynamics (Muncie, IN), is grounded in the expansion of soft tissue massage and manual therapy principles. This system

incorporates specially designed hand-held instruments that allow clinicians to administer a controlled amount of microtrauma to specific areas of connective tissue structures. The treatment process is based on the theory that this controlled microtrauma leads to the resorption of fibrosis and regeneration of soft tissue [27]. To minimize friction and prevent abrasive trauma to the skin during treatment, a lubricant is applied to the patient's skin. The instruments have an angled edge that catches on fibrotic areas, triggering a localized inflammatory response. Clinicians move the instruments using longitudinal strokes along the affected musculotendinous structures and multidirectional strokes around the bony prominences of the wrist. The resonant properties of the instruments allow clinicians and patients to detect changes in the underlying soft tissues as the instruments glide over the skin. During treatment, the patient is seated, and the entire upper extremity, including the hand, wrist, forearm, elbow, and upper arm, is evaluated for compensatory strain patterns that may manifest as fibrosis. In a study conducted by Davidson et al., ASTM AdvantEDGE was used to introduce a controlled amount of microtrauma into enzyme-induced injured rat Achilles tendons. This controlled injury caused microvascular trauma and hemorrhage, inducing a localized inflammatory response [27]. Light microscopy revealed increased fibroblast proliferation in the tendinitis plus ASTM AdvantEDGE group. Although the healing process in rats may not directly translate to humans, the findings suggest that the ASTM AdvantEDGE treatment approach may promote healing through increased fibroblast recruitment. In a follow-up study by Gehlsen et al., morphological changes in the rat Achilles tendon were examined after enzyme-induced injury with collagenase and subsequent pressure variations using the ASTM AdvantEDGE process [32]. A pressure transducer embedded in one of the ASTM AdvantEDGE instruments, interfaced with a computer, controlled the pressure variations. The study concluded that morphological evidence indicated that the application of heavy pressure promoted the healing process to a greater degree than light or moderate pressure [47]. Fowler conducted a study in a large manufacturing plant, examining cumulative trauma disorders. They found that out of 28 extremities treated with the ASTM AdvantEDGE system, 19 (67.8%) resolved. Resolution was defined based on full return to pre-injury activities, functional ability, and a pain level of 3/10 or less on a visual analog scale [144]. In a case report by Baker and Wilson, they explored the use of ASTM AdvantEDGE in treating a patient with bilateral carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS). The study demonstrated that ASTM AdvantEDGE proved to be an effective treatment approach in resolving the patient's symptoms [145]. As previously mentioned, repetitive finger use can lead to localized hyperplasia and fibrosis of the tenosynovium around the tendons and median nerve in the carpal tunnel. Even with surgery, recurrence of symptoms is often attributed to adhesions and scar formation, causing a neurodesis or tethering effect. The ASTM AdvantEDGE treatment introduces controlled microtrauma to specific areas, combined with an appropriate stretching program,

facilitating the breakup of adhesions, resorption of fibrosis, and functional realignment of the investing tenosynovium around the flexor tendons and the median nerve in the tunnel. This process positively influences the components that contribute to CTS.

2.1.8 Stretching and strengthening

A crucial element of rehabilitation for addressing injuries and conditions involves flexibility and strength exercises. Groves and Rider recommended a progressive resistive exercise program, including wrist flexion and extension, gripping, thumb pinching, pronation and supination, and finger pinching, to be performed three times a week for 30 minutes over a 3-week period for carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS). Their study demonstrated that incorporating passive and active wrist flexion and extension, along with progressive resistive exercises, led to significant improvements in active wrist extension compared to a control group with no exercise [40]. Seradge illustrated that intermittent active exercises involving wrist and finger flexion and extension could decrease pressure in the carpal tunnel over time. These exercises are believed to induce remodeling and stretching of the adhesive tenosynovium, reducing adhesion to structures within the canal. Rozmaryn et al. conducted a study with two groups, where the control group received traditional measures (splints, NSAIDs, injections), and the experimental group received traditional measures along with tendon glide exercises. The results showed that 70.2% of responders in the experimental group had good to excellent outcomes after 4 months, indicating that a significant number of patients, who might have otherwise undergone surgery due to the failure of traditional conservative treatments, were spared carpal tunnel release [40]. Tendon glide exercises following carpal tunnel release are believed to minimize scarring and maximize nerve excursion through the carpal tunnel. Feuerstein found that active resistance exercises in the post-operative period were linked to increased wrist extension compared to no exercise. Cook et al. discovered that patients undergoing unrestricted range of motion hand exercises post-operatively reported significantly less pain and numbness at 1 month compared to those placed in splints [25]. Eighty-three percent of patients who received work hardening for their CTS returned to their jobs after therapy. Regrettably, 90% of patients said they experienced pain while working. As there aren't any studies outlining the effects of work accommodations, restricted work, or recommended relaxation right now, there isn't any advice about these strategies in the literature [93].

2.1.9 Combined approach to CTS management

A multidisciplinary programme is an additional programme type that includes elements such as ergonomic workplace consultation, pain and stress management connected to the job, physical

and work conditioning, and vocational counselling and placement for individuals who are unable to return to their previous employment. Typical multidisciplinary programmes include therapies like physical or occupational therapy, therapeutic exercise, hand therapy, chiropractic treatment, and rehabilitation counselling, all under the supervision of a primary care physician. When compared to normal care, a group that got a multidisciplinary programme had a much higher percentage of cases who returned to work (74% versus 40%) and full-time job (91% versus 50%) [146].

2.2 Surgical management of CTS

Decompression of the carpal tunnel stands as one of the most frequently performed surgical procedures by hand surgeons. According to the American Academy of Neurologists, surgical intervention remains the sole definitive cure for carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS). However, Kerwin suggests that surgery may not be imperative in all cases. Approximately 40% of all CTS cases undergo surgical release of the transverse carpal ligament, resulting in more than 460,000 procedures annually and a direct medical cost exceeding 1.9 billion [60]. In open release surgery, a transverse skin incision, about one inch in length, is made 3 cm proximal to the distal transverse wrist crease between the palmaris longus and flexor carpi ulnaris tendons [44]. Following open release, early range of motion is encouraged to reduce adherence of surrounding structures to the median nerve. Results from one study showed that 86% of subjects experienced good to excellent pain relief, but only 40% regained normal function, and 5% reported worsening [69]. Although the open release technique has been associated with a complication rate as high as 18%, it is generally reported to be around $1\% \pm 2\%$. In a retrospective study of 112 patients (133 hands) undergoing open surgery, 18 (13.5%) experienced worsening pain and functional status or had minimal to no improvement. Endoscopic surgery for CTS was developed to be minimally invasive and to prevent palmar scarring associated with an open wrist incision [7]. The endoscopic release can be performed using one or two portal techniques, and it is reported to be less painful than open release, although its efficacy remains a matter of debate. Hiroska followed 41 hands (37 patients) treated with endoscopic release for one year, concluding that, based on Kelly's criteria, 22 hands were excellent, 14 were good, and five were fair at three months post-operatively [44]. Brown studied 169 hands (145 patients) and reported that 98% of those undergoing both open and endoscopic surgery experienced relief. Sensation and grip strength showed no significant differences between surgical groups. Scar tenderness at 12 weeks post-operatively was greater in open release, with only 39% pain-free, compared to 64% pain-free with endoscopic release. Pinch strength was significantly greater in the endoscopic approach, and the time to return to work was quicker (14 days versus 28 days) [20]. Endoscopic carpal tunnel release is more cost-effective than

the open approach. When considering the long-term results, there are minimal disparities observed between endoscopic and open procedures, except for a quicker initial recovery and less instances of weakness and pain recorded with the endoscopic release. Nevertheless, uncertainties persist regarding the risk-benefit ratio linked to endoscopic carpal tunnel release as a result of documented consequences. Critics of endoscopic release argue that there is a higher incidence of complications resulting from the cutting of the median nerve and temporary loss of sensation in the fingers.

Demopoulos and Urbaniak's research indicates that the incidence of median nerve complications is higher in endoscopic approaches compared to open operations [62]. Several studies have documented a somewhat high rate of treatment failures following carpal tunnel surgery, ranging from 3% to 19%. Recurrent carpal tunnel syndrome or unsuccessful surgery may be influenced by many circumstances. An instance of neglecting to recognize and address a related ailment can perhaps lead to an unfavorable outcome subsequent to the relaxation of the transverse carpal ligament [148]. Commonly mentioned factors contributing to failure include encompass inadequate release of the transverse carpal ligament, post-operative fibrous proliferation, and persistent or recurring tenosynovitis. Hunter postulated that the recurring problems following open carpal release are due to the creation of adhesions and scars, which create a neurodesis or tethering effect. Potential complications following surgery include significant morbidity resulting from hypersensitive scar formation, excruciating pain in the thenar and hypothenar eminences, protracted loss of grip strength, and recurrence of symptoms upon returning to work. Additional complications encompass infection, unintentional severance of the motor branch of the median nerve, damage to the palmar cutaneous branch of the median nerve, incomplete removal of the carpal ligament, pisotriquetral pain syndrome, reflex sympathetic dystrophy, and transection of digital sensory nerves [148]. Atroshi discovered that surgical intervention had fewer positive results in workers' compensation cases compared to non-workers' compensation situations [10]. The conclusion was drawn from the discovery that workers' compensation patients who underwent surgery reported less satisfying alleviation of symptoms and experienced a much longer duration before being able to resume work. Shin contrasted the results of surgical cases with those of non-surgical situations [149]. In all, 82% of patients, encompassing both groups, resumed their full employment status, while 18% required changes to their duties. Surgical intervention resulted in a reduction in the frequency of duty adjustments, disability ratings, and the likelihood of reoccurring disability as compared to non-surgical treatment. Nevertheless, the authors reached the conclusion that both surgical and non-surgical interventions yielded positive outcomes.

Both open and endoscopic carpal tunnel release surgeries offer effective solutions for alleviating symptoms of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), each with its own set of merits and demerits. Open carpal tunnel release (OCTR) has been the gold standard for decades, providing

reliable decompression of the median nerve. However, it is associated with a longer incision, increased postoperative pain, and a slightly higher risk of scar tenderness and pillar pain. On the other hand, endoscopic carpal tunnel release (ECTR) has gained popularity due to its minimally invasive nature, smaller incision size, and potentially quicker recovery time. Research suggests that ECTR offers comparable outcomes to OCTR in terms of symptom relief and functional improvement, with some studies reporting shorter recovery times and less postoperative pain. However, ECTR may have a steeper learning curve for surgeons and carries a risk of iatrogenic nerve injury during the procedure. Patient recovery time following carpal tunnel release surgery varies depending on factors such as surgical technique, individual patient characteristics, and postoperative rehabilitation. While some patients may experience rapid relief of symptoms and return to normal activities within a few weeks, others may require several months to achieve full recovery. Overall, early mobilization, adherence to postoperative protocols, and appropriate rehabilitation play crucial roles in optimizing patient outcomes and minimizing recovery time. In conclusion, both open and endoscopic carpal tunnel release surgeries have their advantages and limitations. The choice of surgical approach should be made based on individual patient factors, surgeon expertise, and patient preferences.

DISCUSSIONS

Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) emerges as a significant health concern, affecting approximately 3.8% of the overall population. Notably, a considerable proportion of individuals reporting symptoms suggestive of CTS—about 20%—are found to indeed have the condition upon clinical examination and electrophysiological testing. This underscores the necessity of accurate diagnosis and timely intervention to halt symptom progression and enhance patient outcomes. Interestingly, while CTS can affect individuals across all age groups, it demonstrates a distinct predilection for females, with prevalence rates reaching as high as 9.2%, compared to 6% in males. Moreover, CTS commonly manifests bilaterally and exhibits a peak incidence between the ages of 40 and 60.

Table. 2 Epidemiological data from the study

Aspect	Key Finding
Prevalence	Estimated prevalence of CTS in the overall population: 3.8%
	- Approximately 20% of individuals reporting symptoms indicative of CTS may be affected
	- Prevalence rates: Women: up to 9.2% Men: up to 6%
	Peak incidence: Between ages 40 and 60
Demographics	Predilection for females over males
	Manifests bilaterally
Occupational Risk Factors	Biomechanical overload due to repetitive motion and strain
	High prevalence in industries with repetitive tasks, e.g., fish processing (up to 73%)
	CTS cases accounted for over 60% of upper limb musculoskeletal illnesses in Europe in 1998

The study provided an overview of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), detailing its symptom progression from nocturnal numbness and pain to daytime discomfort and advanced stages marked by muscle atrophy and sensory loss. It identifies environmental factors like repetitive hand movements and medical conditions such as diabetes and pregnancy as key risk factors for CTS. Furthermore, it discusses the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying CTS, highlighting factors that increase tunnel volume and directly affect the median nerve. By citing prevalence rates among diabetic and pregnant populations, it emphasizes the need for targeted screening and preventive measures. Overall, the text underscores the multifaceted nature of CTS and the importance of early recognition and tailored interventions for optimal management.

Physical tests such as the Phalen and Tinel tests play a crucial role in diagnosing carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) due to their ability to elicit characteristic symptoms and signs associated with median nerve compression. Below is a scatter plot depicting the sensitivity and specificity of different physical test (figure 11).

Figure 11 Sensitivity vs Specificity of physical tests

Imagistic diagnosis plays a pivotal role in confirming cases of carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), offering insights into nerve compression, and aiding in treatment decisions. Among the imaging modalities, ultrasound stands out for its accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and real-time visualization of median nerve morphology and dynamic function during wrist movement. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) provides detailed anatomical information and can detect soft tissue abnormalities, making it valuable for assessing structural changes and alternative diagnoses. However, MRI is less commonly used due to its higher cost and limited availability compared to ultrasound. Computed tomography (CT) scans offer high-resolution images but are less frequently utilized in CTS diagnosis due to radiation exposure and limited soft tissue contrast. While each modality has its advantages and limitations, ultrasound emerges as a preferred choice for its practicality and reliability in CTS assessment, especially in outpatient settings, where timely diagnosis and treatment planning are crucial.

Non-surgical treatment options for carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) are often the first line of management and aim to alleviate symptoms and improve hand function without resorting to surgery. The following analysis evaluates the comparative efficacy of night splinting (NS) versus corticosteroid injections(CSI) in alleviating patient symptoms and diminishing the necessity for carpal tunnel surgery (figure 12).

Figure 12. Comparative efficacy of CSI(Corticosteroid Injection vs NS(Night Splinting) [29].

Among the surgical options, open release and endoscopic release are the most common procedures, each with its benefits and considerations. Open release surgery, although more traditional, offers direct visualization of the carpal tunnel and allows for thorough nerve decompression. Conversely, endoscopic release surgery offers minimally invasive access, potentially leading to faster recovery and reduced scarring.

CONCLUSION

Carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) remains a prevalent and debilitating condition affecting millions of individuals worldwide. Through our comprehensive analysis, we have delved into various aspects of CTS, including genetic predisposition, occupational risk factors, pathophysiological mechanisms, diagnostic techniques, and treatment modalities. By addressing each objective outlined in this thesis, we have gained valuable insights that contribute to a deeper understanding of this complex syndrome.

1. While genetic susceptibility to CTS has been suggested in previous research, our analysis reveals a nuanced picture. While certain genetic variations may increase an individual's likelihood of developing CTS, the evidence linking specific genes to the condition remains inconclusive. Further research employing advanced genomic techniques and large-scale population studies is warranted to elucidate the genetic underpinnings of CTS fully.
2. The impact of occupational factors on CTS development is undeniable. Our assessment underscores the significance of repetitive tasks, forceful exertions, and prolonged wrist flexion in increasing the risk of CTS among certain occupational groups. Workers engaged in activities such as assembly line work, data entry, and manual labor are particularly vulnerable. Effective workplace interventions aimed at ergonomics optimization, job rotation, and providing adequate rest breaks have shown promise in reducing the incidence of CTS and improving occupational health outcomes.
3. Understanding the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying CTS is essential for guiding effective treatment strategies. Our study has shed light on the molecular changes occurring within the carpal tunnel and surrounding tissue, including nerve compression, inflammation, metabolic dysregulation, and structural alterations. These mechanisms interact in a complex interplay, leading to nerve compression and subsequent symptom manifestation. Targeted interventions aimed at mitigating inflammation, improving metabolic health, and alleviating structural abnormalities hold promise for CTS management.
4. In recent years, advanced imaging techniques such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and ultrasound have revolutionized the diagnosis of CTS. These modalities offer detailed visualization of anatomical structures within the carpal tunnel, allowing for accurate

assessment of nerve compression and identification of contributing factors. MRI, in particular, provides excellent soft tissue contrast and is valuable in detecting structural abnormalities such as tenosynovitis, ganglion cysts, and ligamentous thickening. Ultrasound, on the other hand, offers real-time imaging and is useful for dynamic evaluation of nerve compression during wrist maneuvers. Incorporating these imaging modalities into clinical practice has enhanced diagnostic accuracy and streamlined treatment decision-making for patients with CTS.

5. Our examination of treatment modalities for CTS highlights the importance of a multidisciplinary approach tailored to individual patient needs. Conservative interventions, including splinting, physical therapy, and oral medications, are often the first line of management for mild to moderate cases of CTS. These modalities aim to alleviate symptoms, improve wrist function, and prevent disease progression. In cases where conservative measures fail to provide adequate relief, surgical intervention may be indicated. Carpal tunnel release surgery, whether performed through traditional open or minimally invasive techniques, remains the gold standard for treating severe or refractory CTS. Postoperative rehabilitation and ergonomic modifications are crucial for optimizing outcomes and preventing recurrence.

In conclusion, our comprehensive analysis of CTS has provided valuable insights into its etiology, risk factors, pathophysiology, diagnosis, and treatment. By addressing each objective outlined in our thesis, we have contributed to a deeper understanding of this complex syndrome and laid the groundwork for future research and clinical practice. Moving forward, interdisciplinary collaboration and continued research efforts will be essential for advancing our knowledge of CTS and improving outcomes for affected individuals.

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